

Workshop

18–20 September 2024

TWIN2PIPSA

Bioimaging and Spectroscopy for Protein Interactions Analysis

Book of Abstracts

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Program

	Sep 18	Sep 19	Sep 20	
9:30		Advanced Microscopy and Live Cell Imaging Michael Lisby (UCPH)	Extracellular Proteostasis Michele Vendruscolo (UCAM)	
10:00				
10:30		<i>In Vitro</i> and <i>In Vivo</i> Detection of Amyloid Structures Using Fluorescent Antibodies and Dyes Dana Laor Bar-Yosef (TAU)	Proximity Labelling Assays to Detect Protein Interactions in Cells Daniel Bar (TAU)	
11:00				
11:30				Break
12:00		Protein Phase Separation at the Synapse and Alpha-Synuclein Condensates Janin Lautenschläger (UCAM)	Strategies to Design Peptide Binders for <i>In Cellulo</i> Protein Interaction Studies Daniel Bar	
12:30				
13:00		Free Lunch	Free Lunch	Closing Remarks Cláudio Gomes
13:30				
14:00				
14:30	Opening Cláudio Gomes (ULisboa)	Posters Session Pitch Presentations Networking		
15:00	Unravelling Protein Interactions and Transitions at the Nanoscale Francesco Ruggeri (WUR)	Protein Sample preparation for Nanoscale Analysis by AFM Francesco Ruggeri	Networking Laboratory Visits (optional)	
15:30				
16:00	Posters Session Pitch Presentations Networking	Analysis of Phase Separation in Living Cells: An Experimental Overview Janin Lautenschläger		
16:30				
17:00				
17:30	----- Free time -----			

Speakers

Francesco Simone Ruggeri is currently Assistant Professor at Wageningen University (WUR) in the Netherlands. Before he completed his independent Junior Research Fellowship at the Department of Chemistry at University of Cambridge and at the Darwin College (UK), during which he developed and applied single-molecule scanning probe microscopy and spectroscopic methods for the bio-chemical and biophysical characterisation of biomolecular processes at the nanoscale. Overall, Dr. Ruggeri's approach has brought new insights into the formation and structural characterization of misfolding of proteins and their correlation with the onset of neurodegenerative disorders. Moreover, Dr. Ruggeri has developed and applied single molecule AFM-based approaches in combination with microfluidics to study the chemical and structural properties of biological systems that are challenging to access using conventional bulk biophysical methods. He was also the first to demonstrate the application of nanomechanical mapping and infrared nanospectroscopy (AFM-IR) to unravel the properties of biological samples at the nanoscale in air and liquid environments. As major advance in the field of microscopy and spectroscopy, he has recently demonstrated that AFM-IR is capable to acquire the chemical fingerprint and secondary structure of biological samples in native liquid environments and at the single-molecule scale.

Michael Lisby is a Professor at Copenhagen University in Denmark. Following his doctoral studies at Aarhus University in Denmark, Prof. Lisby continued his studies at Columbia University, New York, USA. He then established his laboratory at Copenhagen University, where he focused on exploring the spatio-temporal organization and regulation of homologous recombination (HR) and its role in maintaining genome integrity. Namely, he applies cell biological and genetic approaches to study HR in human cells and the yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. In particular, he aims to investigate the regulation of chromatin structure during HR,

post-translational modification of HR proteins, and the molecular architecture of HR complexes in living cells. Understanding the molecular mechanisms relevant to cancer predisposition, neurological disorders and premature ageing syndromes, and in utilizing homologous recombination in CRISPR-Cas9 gene-editing are at the core of his research.

Dana Laor Bar-Yosef is a molecular biologist and the head of the *in vivo* metabolic research group at Prof. Ehud Gazit's lab. During her post-doctoral research, she applied her extensive experience in yeast analysis to successfully establish the first *in vivo* model for the study of inborn errors associated with metabolism disorders, which can also be linked to the formation of metabolite amyloid-like structures. Dr. Laor Bar-Yosef is currently leading the *in vivo* metabolic research group at Prof. Gazit's lab and has initiated a fruitful collaboration with the BLAVATNIK CENTER for Drug Discovery at Tel Aviv University to establish an integrated drug discovery platform for metabolic disorders. Notably, Dr. Laor Bar-Yosef has recently won the 2020 Ziegler Award for her work in the field of metabolic disorders, a prize dedicated to young scientists with exceptional contribution to research with medical application.

Janin Lautenschläger has a PhD in Neuroscience from the University of Jena, Germany, Dr Janin Lautenschläger is interested in molecular mechanisms involved in neurodegenerative diseases. The current focus of her research lies in the understanding of protein phase separation at the synapse, with implications in health and disease such as Parkinson's.

Michele Vendruscolo is a Professor of Biophysics, Director of the Chemistry of Health Laboratory and Co-Director of the Centre for Misfolding Diseases at the Department of Chemistry of the University of Cambridge. His research has been focused on the development of methods for characterising the structure, dynamics, and interactions of proteins in previously inaccessible states. Namely, these new approaches aim to obtain information about a variety of protein conformations, as for example those populated during the folding process, and about protein interactions in complex environments, including those generating aggregate species that are associated with neurodegenerative disorders such as Alzheimer's and Parkinson's diseases; thus, establishing the fundamental principles of protein homeostasis and protein aggregation.

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Daniel Bar is a Senior Lecturer at the Tel Aviv University and is the head of the Molecular Biology of Aging lab. After completing his doctoral studies on genetics at the Hebrew University of Jerusalem, he was a visiting fellow at the Collins lab, at the National Institutes of Health (NIH), during which he applied on proximity labelling and single-molecule detection approaches to assess protein-DNA interactions. Currently, he is focused on the development of new methods and use them to answer questions related to aging. These include novel approach to determine the local protein environment near targets of interest in human samples, identification of protective natural antibodies in Alzheimer's disease, and the identification of a class methylation sites where epigenetic information is lost in aging, stress and disease.

Lectures

Unravelling Protein Interactions and Transitions at the Nanoscale

Francesco Simone Ruggeri

Wageningen University and Research

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A key challenge in biosciences is the comprehension of how the physical-chemical state and heterogeneity of biomolecules determine their role in cellular function and disease, such as in the case of protein condensation, self-assembly and its role in cell toxicity and the onset of neurodegenerative disorders. Here, we demonstrate that Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) based techniques can contribute to shed light onto the molecular and structural basis of functional and pathological protein interactions and self-assembly. AFM can resolve the complex and heterogeneous conformational states involved in protein misfolding and self-assembly at the single molecule scale with angstroms resolution. For the first time, we identify on pathway of aggregation novel intermediate and elongated pre-fibrillar species, possessing sub-nanometre diameter, which we termed single strand protofilaments. We demonstrate that these new species cause neuroinflammatory response and form directly from the assembly of monomers both in-vitro and in ex-vivo human samples. We then develop and apply infrared nanospectroscopy (AFM-IR) to study amyloids at the single-molecule level and unravel their morphological, mechanical, and chemical-structural properties. This unprecedented sensitivity can be used in turn to study the molecular interaction of pathological amyloid with small molecules able to prevent aggregation in-vitro and in animal models of disease.

References:

- [1] Miller, *PNAS*, 2023
- [2] Lobanova, *Brain*, 2022
- [3] Emin, *Nature Comm*, 2022
- [4] Ruggeri, *Nature Comm*, 2021
- [5] Ruggeri, *Nature Comm*, 2020

Advanced Microscopy and Live Cell Imaging

Michael Lisby

Copenhagen University

Advanced live cell microscopy provides access to obtain information about single cells and even single molecules within cells as a function of time, which cannot be obtained from population averages. The advantages and disadvantages of various microscope techniques and reagents will be discussed with special focus on protein-protein interactions and dynamics. The key methods that will be introduced are fluorescence redistribution after photobleaching (FRAP), bimolecular fluorescence complementation (BiFC), fluorescence resonance energy transfer (FRET), and fluorescence life-time imaging.

***In vitro* and *in vivo* detection of amyloid structures using fluorescent antibodies and dyes**

Dana Laor Bar-Yosef

Tel Aviv University

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The formation of proteinaceous amyloids has been investigated for decades from biological, physical, and clinical perspectives. In a series of studies, we extended this hypothesis to include amyloid-like self-assemblies formed by various metabolites, thereby pioneering the field of metabolite self-assembly into nanofibrillar structures. We have demonstrated the formation of ordered nanostructures by several metabolites, including amino acids and nucleobases. These assemblies exhibit physicochemical properties that closely resemble those of protein amyloids, such as morphology, specific fluorescent dye binding, electron diffraction patterns, immunological responses, and cytotoxicity. Additionally, we have identified the presence of metabolite supramolecular structures in inborn errors of metabolism (IEM) disorders, underscoring their significance in a range of pathologically diverse diseases.

As metabolite amyloids represent unique immunological entities with distinct epitopes, producing antibodies against these amyloid assemblies can greatly advance the study of amyloid pathology. Studies conducted in our lab have demonstrated that several types of metabolite fibrils can be specifically detected using antibodies raised against the assembled structures. Moreover, antibodies purified from the serum of IEM patients can be employed as primary antibodies, with *in vitro* assembled metabolite fibrils serving as antigens. Detection has been observed in cell cultures, patient tissues, body fluids, and *in vivo* models. In addition to the study of metabolite assemblies *in vitro*, *in vivo* models are also being explored for amyloid fibril detection. Using flow cytometry, we have shown increased intracellular amyloid staining *in vivo* with amyloid-specific fluorescent dyes. Additionally, aggregation can be monitored using specific antibodies targeting these assemblies.

Protein Phase Separation at the Synapse and Alpha-Synuclein Condensates

Janin Lautenschläger

Cambridge University

α -Synuclein (α SYN), a pivotal synaptic protein implicated in synucleinopathies such as Parkinson's disease and Lewy body dementia, undergoes protein phase separation. We reveal that vesicle-associated membrane protein 2 (VAMP2) orchestrates α SYN phase separation both in vitro and in cells. Electrostatic interactions, specifically mediated by VAMP2 via its juxtamembrane domain and the α SYN C-terminal region, drive phase separation. Condensate formation is specific for R-SNARE VAMP2 and dependent on α SYN lipid membrane binding. Furthermore, we show that α SYN condensates sequester vesicles and attract complexin-1 and -2, thus supporting a role in synaptic physiology and pathophysiology.

Extracellular Proteostasis

Michele Vendruscolo

Cambridge University

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Proximity Labelling Assays to Detect Protein Interactions in Cells

Daniel Bar

Tel Aviv University

Protein functionality is intricately linked to their assemblies and interactions, which exhibit complex spatial and temporal organization within cells. To better understand protein function, it's often beneficial to analyze proteins alongside their neighboring molecules. However, protein-protein interactions occur across a wide spectrum of affinity and duration. Proximity labeling offers an alternative approach by targeting proteins near the molecule of interest, regardless of their binding affinity. We will review current proximity labeling techniques and outline a protocol for antibody-directed tag deposition in fixed and permeabilized cell lines and primary human tissue samples.

Theoretical- Practical Sessions

Protein Sample preparation for Nanoscale Analysis by AFM

Francesco Simone Ruggeri

Wageningen University and Research

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The development of atomic force microscopy (AFM) has opened up a wide range of novel opportunities in nanoscience and new modalities of observation in complex biological systems. AFM nanoscale analysis has been widely employed to resolve the complex and heterogeneous conformational states involved in protein interactions, condensation and self-assembly at the single molecule scale and shed light onto the molecular basis of a variety of human pathologies, including neurodegenerative disorders.

Here, we will present several case studies on how samples preparation and advanced data analysis can be performed to study protein interactions. First, prior to actual single-molecule AFM measurements, we will illustrate the challenges associated to manual samples deposition and how sample preparation can be complemented by our recently developed single-step microfluidic spray deposition platform. Then, we elucidate the principles for a successful nanoscale analysis of protein self-assembly and condensation, taking as model systems the case of protein and peptides, such as α -synuclein, Ab, FUS, huntingtin.

References

- [1] Miller, *Sci Adv*, 2023
- [2] Ruggeri, *Nature Comm*, 2018
- [3] Ruggeri, *Arch Biochem Biophys*, 2019
- [4] Ruggeri, *ACS Nano*, 2020

Analysis of Phase Separation in Living Cells: An Experimental Overview

Janin Lautenschläger

Cambridge University

This talk will cover various methods used to study protein phase separation in living cells. First, experiments commonly used to characterize biomolecular condensates, which can be applied both in vitro and within cells, will be discussed. Then we will focus on light- and chemically-inducible systems, such as the OptoDroplet, Corelet, iPOLYMER, PixELL, and CasDrop system. Examples where these techniques have been used to assess condensate function will be presented. The last part will highlight recent examples where condensate formation has been linked to functional roles at the synapse such as the attraction of condensate partners and vesicle clustering.

Strategies to Design Peptide Binders for *In Cellulo* Protein Interaction Studies

Daniel Bar

Tel Aviv University

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Designing peptide binders for specific protein targets remains a formidable challenge in drug discovery and chemical biology, yet it holds immense potential for modulating protein-protein interactions (PPIs) implicated in various diseases. The vast sequence space of potential peptides and the complexity of protein-peptide interactions have traditionally limited progress in this field. However, recent advancements in protein modeling artificial intelligence, particularly structure prediction tools like AlphaFold, are poised to revolutionize peptide binder design. Herein we present an in-silico evolution driven approach to address this challenge. Our method employs a three-pronged strategy: (1) generating binding candidates using native protein substrates and generative models, (2) in-silico mutagenesis and rapid screening based on energy calculations (3) de novo complex structure prediction using multiple models. We demonstrate this method's efficacy using the insulin-like growth factor 1 receptor (IGF1R) as a model system. Through iterative in-silico evolution and structure prediction with AlphaFold, we designed optimized FnIII-2-like peptides (pep8 and pep9) targeting the L1 domain of IGF1R. These peptides showed enhanced binding affinity in silico, partly mediated by newly incorporated tryptophans interacting with a hydrophobic groove in the L1 domain. In vitro validation using ELISA and fluorescence polarization assays confirmed the binding hierarchy: pep9 > pep8 > pep0 (original sequence). Live cell imaging in HeLa cells expressing IGF1R further corroborated these findings, with pep9 demonstrating robust binding across multiple cellular foci. This AI-driven approach opens new avenues for designing peptide modulators for previously undruggable targets, with broad implications for drug discovery and biological research.

Posters

Chaperone Multimers Suppress the Generation of A β 42 Neurotoxic Oligomers Implicated in Alzheimer's Disease

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Alzheimer's disease (AD) involves extracellular aggregation of A β 42 into toxic oligomers and fibrils, whose emergence is regulated by molecular chaperones. These include S100B alarmin, a homodimeric EF-hand protein with intra and extracellular functions which acts as a Ca²⁺-switched A β 42 anti-aggregation chaperone. However, S100B occurs also as a homotetramer, with uncharacterized neuroprotective roles. Here, we compared the chaperone activities of both S100B multimers and explored their impact on the formation of A β 42 oligomers (A β O). S100B anti-aggregation activity was evaluated by thioflavin-T (ThT) A β 42 aggregation assays. A β 42 conformers targeted by S100B were accessed by computational and structural-biophysical spectroscopies. A β 42 oligomer distributions were determined through mechanistic analysis of fibril formation and via early detection of A β 42 species using the X-34 fluorophore. A β 42 aggregation kinetics revealed that, unlike the dimer, tetrameric S100B delays A β 42 aggregation and reduces the amounts of fibrils formed at sub/equimolar ratios, an effect that persists even in the absence of Ca²⁺ binding. Structural analysis revealed that this enhanced catalytic efficiency results from a secondary Ca²⁺-independent binding site formed upon tetramerization of S100B, with which monomeric and fibrillar A β 42 interact (Figueira *et al.* 2022 *JMB*). Kinetic and mechanistic analysis revealed that dimeric and tetrameric S100B preferentially inhibit A β 42 fibril surface-catalyzed nucleation, decreasing the reactive influx towards oligomers down to <10%. Such results comply with an independent screening of A β O using a combination of the thioflavin-T and X-34 fluorophores (Figueira *et al.* 2023 *Front Neurosci*). Our study sheds new insights on the functional landscape of S100B chaperone multimers, suggesting its critical role in the regulation of proteopathic A β 42 aggregation and oligomerization in AD.

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Exploiting Anti-S100B VHHs as Tools to Modulate Tau Aggregation by Direct Interactions with Tau Species

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Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a neurodegenerative disorder characterized by the World Health Organization as a public health priority. The pathology is characterized by the aggregation of amyloid- β and tau protein into amyloid- β plaques and neurofibrillary tangles, respectively. Neuroinflammation is also implicated in AD and is responsible for the secretion of alarmins, including the S100B protein. S100B is a protein highly studied in the context of AD and it is known for its dual role as a detrimental pro-inflammatory mediator or a beneficial anti-aggregation chaperone. These characteristics makes S100B an amenable drug target. Given the attractiveness of targeting molecular chaperones with anti-aggregation activity, a library of single-domain antibodies (VHHs) targeting S100B was developed to modulate its functions. Our study explored how these VHHs could enhance S100B anti-aggregation activity and modulate tau aggregation. Using ThT-monitored kinetics of tau₂₄₄₋₃₇₂ aggregation, we unravelled that some VHHs targeting S100B could potentiate S100B inhibitory effect, likely by harnessing S100B in a more competent conformation to bind tau. Unexpectedly, control experiments showed that some anti-S100B VHHs could by themselves inhibit tau₂₄₄₋₃₇₂ aggregation even at sub-stoichiometric levels. This striking observation arises from direct interactions between the VHHs and tau likely to occur between the aggregation-prone regions of the two proteins. Further mechanistic analysis revealed that different nanobodies target various steps of tau fibrillation, interacting with distinct tau species throughout the aggregation process.

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Chaperone Regulation of Tau Liquid-Liquid Phase Separation

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The phenomenon of liquid-liquid phase separation (LLPS) involving tau is increasingly acknowledged as a contributory process in the onset of tau aggregation and the generation of pathogenic conformers within Alzheimer's disease (AD). Neuroinflammation accompanies tau pathology, with late-stage astrocyte-released alarmin exacerbating the condition, while early inflammatory responses encompass protective functions. This applies to the Ca^{2+} -binding protein S100B, which we recently implicated as a proteostasis-regulator that inhibits amyloid-beta (Cristovão *et al.* 2018 *Sci Adv*) and tau aggregation/seeding (Moreira *et al.* 2021 *Nat Commun*). These findings suggest a broad holdase-type chaperone function for S100B in counteracting the malformation of protein structures. Our study aims to elucidate S100B's role in tau LLPS. PEG-induced tau LLPS was followed by spectroscopy measurements of light absorbance (400nm) and tau fluorescently labelled. Co-localization of S100B within tau droplets was achieved using fluorescence-labelled proteins and FLIM-FRET. Evaluation of droplet fluidic characteristics encompassed fluorescence recovery after photobleaching (FRAP) and observation of fusion events. Phase diagrams indicate significant suppression of tau droplet formation by Ca^{2+} -S100B, preserving droplet liquid properties. Introduction of Ca^{2+} to PEG-induced LLPS with apo-S100B promptly reduces tau droplet levels, highlighting the dynamic, calcium-triggered nature of Ca^{2+} -S100B's action. Likewise, S100B effectively halts PEG-free Zn^{2+} -induced tau LLPS due to its combined Zn^{2+} -buffering and tau-interaction capabilities. Our results establish S100B as a calcium-dependent suppressor of tau LLPS. Collectively, these findings suggests that S100B, functioning as a chaperone, regulates the formation of various pathological conformers and phase-separated systems, strengthening its pivotal role as a proteostasis regulator in early neurodegeneration.

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Interplay Between Tau Aggregation and Phase Separation: Chaperone-mediated Regulation and New Potential Research Venues

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Tau is an intrinsically disordered protein involved in several neurodegenerative tauopathies, including Alzheimer's Disease (AD). While one of the main aspects of tau pathology is the appearance of fibrillar aggregates in the brain, recent evidence has shown that tau is also able to phase separate. So far, the biological context and physiological relevance of tau phase separation has not yet been fully elucidated. In this regard, it is unclear if this process could be accelerating tau self-assembly towards fibrillar amyloids, or if it is acting as a safeguarding mechanism, potentially involving endogenous cofactors. With this in mind, we aim to combine *in silico*, *in vitro* and *in cell* approaches, looking to gain further insights regarding the interrelation between tau phase separation and aggregation. We recently demonstrated that the brain protein S100B functions as a chaperone, inhibiting both tau aggregation and PS, by partitioning into tau droplets. Building on this, we employed CALVADOS, a coarse-grained model capable of predicting phase separation properties, to support our *in vitro* experimental findings, showing that tau is able to undergo phase separation independently but reverts to a single phase in the presence of S100B. Developing this further, we are now expanding our *in vitro* and *in silico* analyses towards a wider array of S100 proteins which are known to be expressed in the brain and have been implicated in AD pathways. Moving forwards, we also strive to use cellular approaches to study environmental factors that influence the pathological aggregation and phase separation of tau, working towards enhancing our mechanistic understanding of these processes while contextualizing their physiological significance within the broader contexts of health and disease.

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S100A9 Self-assembles Into Pseudo-amyloid Fibrils Formed by Native Globular Protomers

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The S100A9 protein, a proinflammatory cytokine from the S100 family associated with aging, is increasingly expressed in neurodegenerative diseases. Recent research indicates that elevated levels of S100A9 during inflammation may promote its amyloidogenesis and deposition, particularly through exposure of aggregation-prone regions in helix IV and C-terminal region. This mechanism has been proposed in the context of neurodegenerative disorders (Wang *et al.* 2018 *Sci Rep*) in which S100A9 co-aggregates intracellularly, contributing to the formation of fibrillar structures (Wang *et al.* 2019 *Neurosci Lett*). However, the structure characterization of these fibrils remains incompletely established and lacks a well-defined mechanistic understanding. Here we investigate the spontaneous formation of S100A9 polymeric assemblies under physiological conditions. Our findings indicate that S100A9 soluble fibrils retain native-like structural properties: S100A9 string-like polymeric structures are highly stable, are soluble and can be resolved by SEC from S100A9 dimers, while retaining the S100A9 α -helical fold although exhibiting a slight increase in intermolecular parallel β -sheets, as revealed by circular dichroism and ATR-FTIR spectroscopy. Analysis of atomic force microscopy (AFM) data reveals that each single protofilament is a chain of

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protomers that consist of S100A9 dimers that further hierarchically assemble into thicker fibrils, forming double protofilaments. While the single protofilaments showed a flexible rod morphology, the double protofilaments showed a helical twist morphology, similarly to α -Syn (Ruggeri *et al.* PNAS 2018). In agreement, the S100A9 filaments have nanomechanical properties distinct to those of bona fide amyloids fibrils. We hypothesized that the unstructured C-terminal region of S100A9, unique among its protein family, drives this multimerization into these pseudo-amyloids. Using tryptophan fluorescence and acrylamide quenching studies, we identified the C-terminal region as the interaction site between dimers, indicated by reduced solvent accessibility of the tryptophan 89 at the C-terminal segment. Computational studies further supported the involvement of the C-terminal region in S100A9 multimerization. To validate this experimentally, we compared the S100A9 C3S variant with a mutant lacking the C-terminal region (S100A9 C3S Δ 90). Our results showed that the Δ 90 mutant failed to polymerize, confirming the essential role of the C-terminal region in polymeric structure formation. We speculate that this spontaneous quaternary structure organization of S100A9 may stabilize the protein and extend its lifespan in extracellular environments, particularly in the synapse, without limiting its function or dimer availability.

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P6

Exploring TDP-43 Modulation in Neurodegenerative Proteinopathies: The Impact of Chaperones and RNA on Phase Separation, Aggregation, and Cellular Localization

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Transactive response DNA-binding protein 43 (TDP-43) proteinopathy is a prominent feature of amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) and tau-negative frontotemporal dementia, and emerging evidence links it to other neurodegenerative disorders like Alzheimer's disease. TDP-43 is a nucleic acid-binding protein that shuttles between the nucleus and cytoplasm where it plays important roles in RNA metabolism, regulating transcription, translation, mRNA splicing, transport and stabilization, non-coding RNA processing, and assembly of membraneless organelles such as cytoplasmic stress granules (SGs) in neurons. Current research indicates that the mechanisms underlying TDP-43 neuropathology consist of nuclear loss-of-function and cytoplasmic gain-of-function through depletion of TDP-43 in the nucleus and mislocalization and further aggregation in the cytoplasm. Furthermore, it has been evidenced that misfolded TDP-43 might propagate toxicity in a prion-like manner. In physiological conditions, TDP-43 undergoes liquid-liquid phase separation (LLPS) to form membraneless organelles, contributing to the spatiotemporal control of RNA processing in the nucleus. In pathology, TDP-43 suffers cleavage resulting in cytoplasmic accumulation of C-terminal fragments (CTFs) containing the intrinsically disordered low-complexity domain of TDP-43, which has been shown to be sufficient to initiate LLPS in vitro. Furthermore, it has been suggested that mislocalization of CTFs in the cytoplasm can recruit full-length TDP-43 and enhance the transition of TDP-43 liquid droplets into a solid state, leading to spontaneous aggregation and neurodegeneration. S100B is an astrocytic alarmin, expressed both in the nucleus and cytoplasm, that interacts with various cellular components, including transcription factors and microtubules. Notably, S100B exhibits neuroprotective chaperone activity, inhibiting aggregation of amyloid β and tau, suggesting a potential role in

maintaining protein homeostasis. This project aims to investigate whether the S100B chaperone is implicated in regulating TDP-43 function under physiological conditions, and uncover novel mechanisms involved in TDP-43 regulation, critical for understanding proteostasis and identifying therapeutic targets like S100B to counter pathological protein interactions.

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P7

Exploring the Role of Sacsin and S100B in Cytoskeleton Organization in ARSACS Glial Model

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Autosomal recessive spastic ataxia of Charlevoix-Saguenay (ARSACS) is a neurodegenerative disorder caused by mutations in the SACS gene, resulting in defective forms of the protein saccin. The biological role of saccin is barely known, although it displays chaperone activity and is related to mitochondrial behavior and function. While ARSACS studies have focused on neuronal cells, we observed high levels of saccin in astroglia, as well as microglia, leading us to develop glial cell models of ARSACS to study their role in the disorder. Saccin knockout (KO) leads to intermediate filaments (IFs) accumulation in the juxtannuclear area. In C6 astroglial cell model, we also observed an upregulation of the S100B chaperone upon saccin deletion. S100B can play a protective role in neurodegenerative disorders by interfering with the formation of toxic protein aggregates. The main goal of this study was to understand the possible relationship between saccin, S100B and cytoskeleton organization. *Sacs*^{-/-} C6 cells exhibited S100B accumulation near IF aggregates. siRNA- or pentamidine-induced inhibition of S100B led to increased mitochondrial fragmentation and circularity of IF aggregates. Higher concentrations of exogenous S100B reduced IF circularity and increased IF area distribution throughout the cell. Advanced microscopy techniques, such as FLIM and FRET, can help us investigate the interaction between saccin, S100B and IFs. Additionally, we are developing a pharmacological model using Withaferin A, an inhibitor of vimentin organization. This drug induces juxtannuclear aggregation of glial IFs, resembling *Sacs*^{-/-} cell phenotype, but did not increase S100B levels. Our results may provide relevant information for the future treatment of ARSACS but also advance our basic understanding of the function of saccin and S100B proteins.

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Unveiling New Horizons: Proton Therapy's Potential in Tackling Neurodegenerative Disorders

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Ionizing radiation is crucial in medical applications, ranging from diagnostics to therapy. Radiation therapy (RT) is widely used in cancer treatment and is now being investigated for its potential to treat extra-cranial amyloidosis and amyloid-related neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's, Parkinson's, and Huntington's diseases. Emerging RT modalities, including proton therapy (PT), offer enhanced biological effects with reduced toxicity, creating new therapeutic possibilities. Proton therapy is particularly advantageous due to its superior depth dose distribution, reduced lateral spread, and minimal scatter, which decrease damage to healthy tissues compared to conventional photon and electron therapies. While PT is well-established in oncology, its application to neurodegenerative diseases remains underexplored. Our research focuses on the use of various radiation modalities, including PT, to target amyloid proteins implicated in these diseases. Ionizing radiation may disrupt amyloid structures by breaking chemical bonds or inducing cellular degradation pathways. Using Monte Carlo simulations (TOPAS and Geant4), we model the effects of radiation on amyloid deposits, with experimental validation underway. Preliminary gamma-irradiation studies on cell lines expressing neurodegenerative proteins showed a dose-dependent reduction in pathological protein levels, which was confirmed through photon and electron

irradiation experiments using a clinical linear accelerator. Ongoing proton therapy experiments, supported by dosimetry measurements, aim to further assess its efficacy. Additionally, an in vitro model is being developed to study radiation effects on protein aggregation, with Thioflavin T as a probe. Our goal is to extend PT applications to neurodegenerative diseases, offering new strategies for their treatment. We aim to study the impact of radiation on abnormal protein-protein interactions in live cells, using advanced microscopy techniques like FLIM and FRET. Our research has the potential to expand the clinical use of PT and contribute to innovative treatments for currently incurable neurodegenerative disorders.

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SPAX8-related Mutations in NKX6-2 Form Stable Aggregates

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NKX6-2, a transcriptional factor, influences neurons, oligodendrocytes, and pancreas cell fates, as well as myelin formation and maintenance. Loss-of-function mutations of NKX6-2 are the cause of Spastic Ataxia 8 (SPAX8), a childhood-onset neurodegenerative disease characterized by hypomyelinating leukodystrophy. Our previous work explored SPAX8-related mutations in a NKX6-2-Venus fluorescent protein fusion system, where we noted the aggregation process in most cases. Currently, we are investigating the nature of these aggregates using timelapse microscopy and FRAP assays, observing that SPAX8-related mutations form solid and stable aggregates. In parallel, we are using bioinformatic databases and tools, such as AlphaFold 3.0, to uncover possible insights on NKX homeodomain's interaction with DNA and tinman domain's interaction with the Gro/TLE family. As it was previously observed that the repression complexes form by Gro/TLE family are important for optimal function of multiple proteins of the Sonic the Hedgehog pathway during neuron cell fate, including some members of the NKX family. In the future, we intend to use FLIM and FRET techniques to study protein complementation of SPAX8 related nonsense mutations and their complementary N-terminus truncations, as well as verify NKX6-2 and TLE interaction in live cells. Our aim is to understand the molecular mechanisms behind SPAX8 and NKX6-2 as whole, as an important step to design a therapeutic strategy for this rare disorder.

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P10

Direct and Indirect Interactions Between Signal Transducer And Activation Of Transcription 3 (STAT3) and NF- κ B/RelA

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Signal Transducer and Activation of Transcription 3 (STAT3) and Nuclear factor-kappa B (NF- κ B) are key transcription factors in several physiological conditions, such as cell growth, survival, development and immune responses. However, they are also major players in pathological conditions, like cancer. STAT3 and the p65 subunit of NF- κ B (RelA), interact in both direct and indirect manners. They can interact by feedback loops mediated by cytokines, i.e. leukemia inhibitory factor (LIF) and tumor necrosis factor α (TNF- α). STAT3 and RelA also interact directly and activate cooperatively transcription of a specific set of genes. For example, when STAT3 is phosphorylated at tyrosine 705 and serine 727, it mediates RelA acetylation, through p300/CBP, increasing its nuclear retention in cancer cells. Nevertheless, the regulatory mechanisms and dynamic of interaction between STAT3 and RelA remain poorly understood. The main aim of this work was to elucidate STAT3 α interplay with RelA, by assessing their heterodimerization and subcellular localization in the absence or presence of stimulating cytokines, i.e. LIF and TNF- α , in HeLa STAT3 $^{-/-}$ cells. To achieve this, we first developed a Bimolecular Fluorescence complementation (BiFC) assay where STAT3 α and RelA were fused to non-fluorescent complementary fragments of the Venus fluorescent reporter. The reconstitution of fluorescence indicates heterodimerization. HeLa STAT3 $^{-/-}$ cells transfected with the STAT3 α and RelA BiFC pair confirmed physical interaction between both proteins and this heterodimer shows the subcellular distribution of RelA/NF- κ B, but the ability of responding to LIF typical of STAT3. In the future, we aim to validate these findings through the application of Fluorescence Lifetime Imaging Microscopy (FLIM) in conjunction with Förster Resonance Energy Transfer (FRET). Our findings enhance our understanding of the interplay between STAT3 and NF- κ B signalling pathways and may contribute to the study of widespread human pathologies, including cancer.

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Biomimetic Adhesives: New Adhesive Proteins Inspired in Sea Urchin Nectin Structural Domains

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Currently, there is a great need in biomedicine and biotechnology for biological adhesives that are non-cytotoxic and efficient in wet/humid environments (*i.e.*, surgical adhesives or cellular adhesion promoters for *in vitro* cultures). It is already known that marine invertebrates are able to attach to several substrates in the presence of seawater (high dielectric and ionic strength similar to physiological fluids) through the production of adhesive secretions. Some of which already inspired the development of new biomimetic adhesives (*i.e.*, Cell-Tak™, a formulation containing proteins from marine mussel). However, successful examples are still scarce and there is still a need for new adhesive systems, with novel capabilities. Sea urchins bioadhesives are an ideal framework to develop new bioinspired adhesives due to their adhesion strengths up to 0.5 MPa, which are higher than commercially available biological adhesives (*e.g.*, fibrin glue 0.2 MPa). Our group has been studying sea urchins' adhesion, focusing on *Paracentrotus lividus*. For this species, Nectin was identified as an important adhesive protein present in both adhesive organs and secretions. It has six galactose-binding discoidin-like (DS) domains, which are thought to be important for its adhesive function. Aiming to develop a new biomimetic adhesive inspired in sea urchins' Nectin, we are currently producing recombinant full-length Nectin and several combinations of its DS domains (constructs), to obtain a stable and scalable adhesive protein for future cell-based applications. To do so, several *E. coli* strains, and growth conditions were tested. The best targets were purified using a combination of chromatographic methodologies, and protein quality was evaluated using biochemical methods.

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The top targets were characterized in respect to structure, conformational stability, aggregation propensity, and adhesive strength, using techniques like circular dichroism (CD), fluorescence, TEM, AFM, and surface coating assays. By now, we were able to express the full-length protein and 5 out of 7 constructs. Furthermore, at least one construct was purified with a 90-95% purity and structurally characterized. Circular dichroism spectra indicate that the purified construct presents a folded conformation. Interestingly, in the presence of high concentrations of certain salts, the construct appears to self-assemble as reported by Thioflavin-T fluorescence binding and TEM imaging, evidencing possible fiber formation. Moreover, preliminary data of surface coating assays indicates that the construct adsorbs to glass surfaces forming a meshwork. Providing a deeper characterization of the first identified sea urchin adhesive protein, this project contributes to enhance the current knowledge on *P. lividus* adhesion mechanisms and opens new avenues for the development of sea urchin inspired bioadhesives for biomedical/biotechnological applications.

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P12

Structural Biology and Biophysical Analysis of the EARS2 Protein and Disease Variants: Unveiling Their Role in Leukoencephalopathy

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Aminoacyl-tRNA synthetases (aaRS) proteins are responsible for adding an amino acid to the corresponding tRNA and, consequently, they are indispensable for the translation process in the cell. Interestingly, mutations in genes encoding for mitochondrial aaRS (mt-aaRS) have been associated to particular mitochondrial disorders (MD), and an increasing number of protein variants are being identified, including in Portugal. Hence, it is essential to clarify the molecular mechanisms behind these MDs and, in particular, to provide information on mt-aaRS structure, conformation, and function to decipher the impact of the identified mutations. We aim to contribute to the field by studying the mitochondrial glutamyl-tRNA synthetase (EARS2), employing biochemical and biophysical methods to make for the first time, to our knowledge, a structural characterization of the human EARS2 wild-type and three disease variants associated with leukoencephalopathy with thalamus and brainstem involvement and high lactate (LTBL). We have heterologously expressed and purified the EARS2 wild-type in *E. coli*, achieving a purity yield higher than 90%. Analysis of secondary and tertiary structure revealed that the purified protein presents a folded conformation, and an apparent melting temperature of 42°C. Regarding disease variants, we established protocols using co-expression with molecular chaperones to increase the bacterial expression yield. We are also optimizing the purification of the EARS2-p.E96K variant. We believe that implementing the purification protocol for this mt-aaRS will open new avenues for characterizing variants and, in the future, aid in designing disease therapies.

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Acylations as Modulators of Mitochondrial Beta Oxidation Proteins

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Metabolic regulation involves a complex interplay of genomic, proteomic and metabolic adjustments within cells. A particular group of non-enzymatic post-translational modification (PTMs) known as acylations, such as succinylation and glutarylation, have emerged as important regulators of mitochondrial enzymes (Wagner *et al.* 2017 *Cell Metab*). The extent of acylations is closely associated with the accumulation of intermediate metabolites such as Succinyl-CoA and Glutaryl-CoA, that occur under certain conditions such as caloric restriction and in several metabolic disorders, creating a unique scenario for anomalous protein acylation (Pougovkina *et al.* 2014 *J Inherit Metab Dis*). Although several studies have identified enzymes that are acylated, and sirtuin substrates (enzymes responsible for modification reversion), the impact at the protein structural and functional level of these modifications remains to be fully addressed. Taking advantage of our know-how with mitochondrial beta oxidation enzymes, we have been studying acylation's impact in different proteins using biochemical and biophysical techniques. We have shown that glutaryl-CoA dehydrogenase (GCDH) is prone to high levels of glutarylation, due to increased glutaryl-CoA production stimulated by lysine catabolism, which diminishes enzyme activity and is regulated by sirtuin5 (Sirt5) (Bhatt *et al.* 2022 *J Biol Chem*). In contrast Medium Chain Acyl-CoA Dehydrogenase (MCAD) and Electron Transfer Flavoprotein (ETF) are prone to succinylation. Interestingly, succinylation increases MCAD activity but decreases ETF activity, although no major differences were shown in neither proteins' structure nor stability. Further, Sirt5 incubation reverts succinylation and brings function of both proteins to unmodified levels.

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